

Landscape-scale patterns and predictors of potato viruses in Scotland

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Abstract

Virus diseases represent important economic threats to seed potato production worldwide, yet relatively little is known of their epidemiology at the landscape-scale. In this study we compiled data from the Scottish national seed potato classification scheme on the incidence of ten different potato viruses for the years 2009-2022. A co-occurrence analysis identified that 12 virus species pairs occurred together more often than expected by chance, and potato blackleg was positively associated with eight potato viruses. ArcGIS was used to investigate spatial and spatiotemporal variation in incidence rates of the three most prevalent viruses (potato virus Y, potato leaf roll virus, potato virus A) and this revealed prominent geographic differences in long-term disease outcomes. We then focused on potato virus Y as the most commonly occurring single infection and used interpretable machine learning techniques to investigate the influence of key crop, management, and environmental factors on patterns of incidence in space and time. The results showed that health characteristics of seed stocks were among the most important predictors of incidence, along with blackleg infection, several management features, cultivar resistance, distance to the nearest seed and ware crop, temperature variables, and several soil features. Our approach provides a comprehensive overview of potato viruses in Scotland, a deeper understanding of epidemiological risk factors at the landscape-scale, and a forecast model that could serve as the basis of a decision support tool for improved management of potato virus Y.

1. INTRODUCTION

Viruses are among the most significant biotic constraints in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) production worldwide (Kreuze et al., 2020). Although more than 50 different viruses have been identified as infecting cultivated potatoes, only a few are reported to have a major impact in terms of their global distribution, incidence and associated yield losses: potato virus Y and its associated strains (such as PVY^O, PVY^C, PVY^N, PVY^{NTN}, family *Potyviridae*, genus *Potyvirus*), potato leafroll virus (PLRV, family *Luteoviridae*, genus *Polerovirus*), potato virus A (PVA, family *Potyviridae*, genus *Potyvirus*), potato virus X (PVX, family *Alphaflexiviridae*, genus *Potexvirus*), potato virus S (PVS, family *Betaflexiviridae*, genus *Carlavirus*), and potato virus M (PVM, family *Betaflexiviridae*, genus *Carlavirus*) (Salazar, 1996, Kreuze et al., 2020, Valkonen, 2007). PVY and PLRV are considered the most damaging viruses of potato worldwide, with PVY having overtaken PLRV as the most important (Kreuze et al., 2020). Early season infection of potato by PVY has been documented as causing tuber yield losses of up to 33%, but planting of infected seed can result in yield losses of up to 80% (Banttari et al., 1993). PVY tuber necrosis strain (PVY^{NTN}) causes a serious disease of potatoes called potato tuber necrotic ringspot disease, which results in dark unsightly rings on tubers that render them unsuitable for fresh market, processing, or seed (Beczner et al., 1984). PLRV can cause similar tuber yield losses and can additionally result in further economic losses through market rejection due to net necrosis, expressed as a network of brown spots and streaks in the vascular tuber tissue (Novy et al., 2007). PVA can cause yield losses of up to 40%, but is far less prevalent worldwide than PVY or PLRV (Kreuze et al., 2020). Mixed infection is often associated with an increase in symptom severity and virus accumulation in comparison to plants infected by these viruses alone, in a phenomenon referred to as synergism (Hull, 2013). For example, PVX alone is not very

destructive but can cause severe losses in combination with other viruses, such as PVY, PVA, and PVS (Barker & Dale, 2006). Similarly, PVS and PVM have mild foliar symptoms that are difficult to characterise, but co-infection together or with PVA can result in severe mosaic, mottle, crinkling, and rolling of leaves (Dolby & Jones, 1987, Rose, 1983).

The Scottish seed potato industry has an excellent reputation worldwide as a reliable supplier of high-health seed potatoes to over 40 countries. It is a significant contributor to Scotland's agricultural sector, accounting for 80% of all UK seed potato production with an estimated annual value of £155 million p.a. (Scottish Government, 2020). Seed potatoes produced and marketed in Scotland must be classified under the Scottish Seed Potato Classification Scheme (SSPCS), which is administered by SASA, a division of the Scottish Government Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate. The SSPCS assures the continuing high health status and purity of Scottish seed potatoes by exerting official control over initial propagating material, the length of the multiplication chain, and application of strict tolerances for diseases, including those caused by viruses. All seed potato crops in Scotland are inspected at least twice during the growing season by trained inspectors, and leaf samples from crops displaying symptoms of viral infection are sent to SASA where they are tested for ten potato viruses: PVY^{O/C/N/NTN}, PVX, PVA, PVS, PVM, PVV, PLRV, tomato black ring virus (TBRV), potato mop-top virus (PMTV), and tobacco rattle virus (TRV).

Among the viruses tested under the SSPCS, PVY, PLRV, PVA, PVV, PVM and PVS can all be transmitted by aphids (Hemiptera: Aphididae). All of these except PLRV are transmitted non-persistently by aphids, whereas PLRV is persistently transmitted (Kumar et al., 2022). Aphid population dynamics are therefore used in Scotland to empower grower decision-making with regards to virus management. Four suction-traps deliver broad, regional information on the

presence and abundance of key aphid species in Scotland to guide insecticide treatment decisions (<https://insectsurvey.com>). Long-term suction-trap data are also combined with weather records to forecast the date of the first aphid flights and abundance in spring and early summer (Pickup et al., 2009, Zhou et al., 1995). It is, however, difficult to predict whether a specific crop will become infected, or whether certain regions are likely to be low- or high-risk for disease. This is because potato virus outbreaks have complex dynamics that are driven by a variety of crop-specific and landscape-scale factors, including, but not limited to, the amount of initial inoculum in potato fields, the spatial arrangement, genetic composition, and general health of potato crops in the landscape, the abundance and distribution of other reservoirs of inoculum, in particular volunteer potato plants and secondary hosts (e.g., weeds), and local weather conditions (Galimberti et al., 2020). This raises a question regarding the possibility of predicting virus incidence at specific locations using information on crops and their surrounding environment, to decipher a 'bigger picture' of potato virus epidemiology beyond the influence of weather on aphid population dynamics.

In this study we analyse a national-scale, longitudinal (2009-2022) dataset on naturally occurring virus infections in seed potato crops from the SSPCS. Our objectives were to: (i) provide an overview of seed potato production and virus incidence in Scotland, (ii) examine the geographic distribution of viruses across Scotland to identify low- and high-risk areas of disease, and (iii) identify important predictors of virus incidence from a range of crop, management, and environmental variables. To meet these objectives, we provided a range of summary statistics concerning seed potato production, virus incidence and species composition. We then used the geostatistical tools of ArcGIS Pro to examine spatial and spatiotemporal patterns of incidence rates of the three most commonly occurring viruses in Scotland (PVY, PLRV, and PVA). For the

modelling component we combined and harmonised national-scale data from various sources to produce an integrated database that included information on crop-specific traits (health and agronomy), seed stock origins, field characteristics (e.g., topography), surrounding seed and ware crop distributions, weather, and soil characteristics. We focused on PVY as the most damaging virus worldwide and the one most commonly occurring as a single infection in Scotland and developed a suite of machine learning classification models to predict space-time patterns of PVY incidence. To gain a deeper understanding of PVY risk factors at the landscape-scale, a model interpretation technique (Shapley values) was used to quantify the relative importance of predictors of disease in the best performing classifier. A simplified version of the classifier was then derived to serve as decision support tool for forecasting patterns of PVY incidence in advance of a growing season. Finally, the information gained from these analyses was used to make several recommendations for improved virus management.

2. METHODS

2.1 Potato virus data used for analysis of patterns of disease

Georeferenced data on incidence (presence/absence in a crop) of 10 different potato viruses from 65,450 seed potato lots in Scotland during 2009-2022 were provided by the Scottish Seed Potato Classification Scheme (SSPCS). (SASA, 2022). Leaf samples from crops displaying visual symptoms were tested for potato viruses (PV) $Y^{O/C/N/NTN}$, X, A, S, M, and V, PLRV, PMTV, and TBRV using ELISA (Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay) and tobacco rattle virus (TRV) using real-time RT-PCR. Note the ELISA test $PVY^{O/C}$ does not discriminate between the serologically related PVY^O , PVY^C and $PVY^{N-Wilga}$ strains while the PVY^N ELISA test does not discriminate between the serologically related PVY^N and PVY^{NTN} strains. A crop was considered infected

with virus if the disease was confirmed in at least one of the inspections during the growing season. Note that the incidence data for PVY in our analyses are for all strains and recombinant variants combined.

2.2 Integrated dataset used for predictive modelling

PVY was by far the most widespread and commonly occurring single infection in the data and is the most important viral pathogen in potato worldwide (Tsedaley, 2015), therefore we focused on prediction of PVY incidence and explanation of the final model. All instances of co-occurrence of PVY with other potato viruses were removed from the data and the single infection incidence data were combined with a range of additional features (variables, or predictors) derived from the SSPCS database: crop features (planting date, seed lot area, potato variety, pre-basic or not, field generation), health features (percentage of rogues, variations to type, volunteer plants, and plants with potato virus symptoms in the crop), management features (percentage of the crop that was pre-rogued and whether the crop was irrigated), and features related to surrounding seed and ware potato crop distributions (Supplementary Table 1). Pre-basic crops are limited to a maximum of four field generations in soil from the original source material and have lower tolerances for disease, including a nil tolerance for PVY/PLRV/PVA, and basic crops are limited to a maximum of seven field generations. Rogues are any undesirable (e.g., diseased) or abnormal plant and pre-roguing is removal of such plants before any inspection date. Variations are ‘off types’ or genetic variants of the same variety, and volunteers are plants that grow from unharvested tubers or cull piles that do not freeze in winter tubers left behind after harvest (Czajkowski et al., 2011). The Potato Variety Database (available at <https://potatoes.agricrops.org/>) was used to convert potato variety to a PVY resistance score, ranging from 1 (low resistance) to 9 (high resistance), where the scores are determined by

comparing the amount of disease developing on candidate varieties with standard reference varieties over multiple years of field trials. In the current study, varietal resistance scores for PVY^O and PVY^N were averaged when both were available, otherwise the score for the available strain was used. To investigate vertical transmission between field generations via latent (unseen) tuber infections, crop, and stock origin identification codes from the SSPCS were used to provide matching incidence, health, and management features of the ‘mother crop’ (seed stock origin) for each seed lot. For percentage health and management features, the maximum value over multiple seasonal inspections was used. The SSPCS data also provided information on surrounding seed and ware potato crop distributions. The slope, elevation and aspect of each seed lot location were extracted from high resolution digital terrain models (DTM). A total of 18 features related to the chemical and physical properties of soil were derived from digital maps provided by Scotland’s Soils (available at <https://soils.environment.gov.scot/>). Hourly weather data from the United Kingdom Meteorological Office was used to calculate a series of 34 bioclimatic variables for each seed lot location, representing long-term averages (within-season and between-season months and quarters, as well as annual averages) of temperature, precipitation, relative humidity, wind speed and wind gusts (O’Donnell & Ignizio, 2012). Weather data were available from 2012 onwards, therefore SSPCS records from 2009-2011 were eliminated from the analysis of risk factors for disease.

2.3 Analysis of patterns of disease

2.3.1 Incidence statistics

Temporal trends of total virus incidence in the SSPCS dataset were evaluated over the study period by field generation (FG), i.e., the number of growing cycles since the first introduction in

the field after micro-propagation or selection. Incidence differences in terms of individual viruses and cultivars were also summarised. To understand patterns of species co-occurrence among the ten potato viruses, the number of single and mixed infections were counted, and a probabilistic species co-occurrence analysis was performed using the *cooccur* function in the R (version 4.3.0) package *cooccur* (version 1.3; Griffith et al., 2016). This classified species pairs as having positive (i.e., co-occur more often than expected by chance alone), negative (i.e., co-occur less often than expected by chance alone), or random associations (i.e., co-occurrence is not different than expected by chance alone) based on the probabilistic model of species co-occurrence (Veech, 2013, Veech, 2014). Incidence of potato blackleg was included in this analysis as a previous study of the SSPCS dataset indicated a potential co-occurrence of blackleg and potato viruses (Skelsey et al., 2023).

2.3.2 Spatial and spatiotemporal patterns of disease

ArcGIS Pro 2.9.3 (Esri UK Ltd, Aylesbury) was then used to map and analyse space and spacetime patterns of incidence of the three most prevalent viruses in the data: PVY, PLRV, and PVA. Note that for the ArcGIS pattern analysis we did not differentiate between single or mixed infections, i.e., incidence was any field where a specific virus was confirmed. To provide an overview of the spatial distribution of seed potato crops and the three viruses during the study period, crop and incidence data were gridded and mapped using a 25 km² hexagonal grid. The Directional Distribution and Central Feature tools were applied to the raw (ungridded) data to provide further insight into the orientation, spread, and central tendency of the virus distributions. For subsequent geostatistical analyses aimed at identifying low- and high-risk areas of disease, grid-based weighted incidence rates (IRW) were used to facilitate detection of non-

random patterns and trends of disease within spatially heterogeneous distributions of seed potato crops:

$$IRW = \frac{\text{Number of infected crops}}{\text{Number of seed potato crops}} \times \frac{\text{Total seed potato area}}{\text{Cell area}}$$

where the first term is the incidence rate per cell, to account for geographic variation in the number of crops, and the second term provides a weighting to account for geographic variation in the spatial coverage of crops. Spatial patterns of virus incidence rates were characterised by analysing the IRW grid for the entire study period (2009-2022) using the Optimised Hot Spot Analysis (OHSA) and Optimised Outlier Analysis (OOA) tools. OHSA calculates Getis-Ord G_i^* statistics (Getis & Ord, 1992) for each grid cell in the data to identify statistically significant high-value (hot spot) and low-value (cold spot) spatial clusters. OOA uses Anselin Local Moran's I statistics (Anselin, 1995) to measure local-level autocorrelations and distinguish four types of spatial clusters and outliers; Low-Low clusters and High-High clusters represent positive local spatial autocorrelation (surrounding areas have similar low or high values of IRW, implying spatial homogeneity), whereas Low-High outliers and High-Low outliers represent negative local spatial autocorrelation (surrounding areas have dissimilar values of IRW, implying spatial heterogeneity). Spatiotemporal patterns of virus incidence rates were characterised by analysing IRW grids for individual years using the Emerging Hot Spot Analysis (EHSA) and Local Outlier Analysis (LOA) tools with a 1-year time interval. EHSA performs two consecutive statistical analyses: Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for spatial evaluation of hot and cold spots, and Mann-Kendall trend test (Kendall & Gibbons, 1990, Mann, 1945) to evaluate up to 17 unique categories of temporal trends in hot and cold spots at each location. LOA is a space-time implementation of the local Anselin Moran's I statistic. Note that we used the OHSA tool to

determine the optimal grid resolution (25 km² hexagonal grid) and scales of analysis (distance band / neighbourhood distance) that were used throughout the study. Further details on these tools can be found in ArcGIS documentation (ESRI, 2022).

2.4 Analysis of predictors of disease

A suite of seven commonly used machine learning algorithms ranging in complexity were developed to classify PVY incidence: discriminant analysis, k -nearest neighbour, decision tree, support vector machine, neural network, random forest, and random undersampling boosting. These are outlined in brief below with references provided for additional details. The MATLAB[®] (version R2023a) commands used to implement the algorithms are provided, and the nested cross-validation procedure used to train, tune, and test the algorithms is described. The best performing model was interpreted using the Shapley value approach from cooperative game theory to identify the most important features for predicting PVY incidence. Code for the above procedures is provided in the Supplement and available from <https://github.com/pskelsey/potatoVirusMachineLearning>.

2.4.1 Data preprocessing

The integrated dataset was prepared for machine learning by removing rows with missing feature values. The data were then gridded in ArcGIS Pro using a 25 km² hexagonal grid, with year of observation used as a grouping variable. Binary (e.g., incidence) and count features were summed, and all other features were averaged. A correlation filter was used to remove 24 strongly correlated ($r > 0.7$) features, producing a final dataset of 2886 values of PVY incidence and 54 features. The prediction problem was reduced to a binary classification task (class 0 = PVY is absent in a grid cell, class 1 = PVY is present in a grid cell). The final dataset was

slightly imbalanced, with PVY absent in 68.4% of grid cells and present in 31.6% of grid cells. The machine learning algorithms described below therefore include a range of techniques to ameliorate the class imbalance in incidence, as this can lead to biased learning towards the majority class: cost functions that penalise misclassification of the minority class, inverse frequency class weighting of observations, and under-sampling of the majority class (Krawczyk, 2016).

2.4.2 Machine learning models

Discriminant analysis (DA) is a classification method that assumes that different classes generate data based on different Gaussian distributions (Klecka, 1980). To create the classifier, Gaussian distribution parameters are estimated for each class and discriminant functions are used to create a decision boundary that maximises the separation between the classes. To make predictions on new data, the trained model finds the class with the smallest misclassification cost. DA was implemented using the *fitcdiscr* function in MATLAB with a cost function to penalise misclassification of the minority class, tuning (optimisation) of the hyperparameters *Delta* (the linear coefficient threshold), *Gamma* (amount of regularisation), and *DiscrimType* (the discriminant type, e.g., linear, quadratic, etc.), and all other settings at default.

The *k*-nearest neighbour classifier (KNN) is one of the simplest and most popular distance-based algorithms. The classification is based on measuring the distance or similarity between test samples and training samples, where data points that are near to each other in the feature space belong to the same class (Ali et al., 2019). KNN was implemented using the *fitcknn* function in MATLAB with a cost function to penalise misclassification of the minority class, tuning of the hyperparameters *NumNeighbors* (the number of nearest neighbours used for classifying each point) and *Distance* (the distance metric), and all other settings at default.

A decision tree (DT) classifier predicts the value of a binary response variable by learning a simple tree-like model of decisions and their possible consequences, similar to a flowchart (Kotsiantis, 2013). The algorithm recursively splits the data into smaller subdivisions based on a series of tests on feature values (decision nodes), and the leaf nodes of the tree are the decisions or final outcomes. DTs are robust, quick to learn, and can capture complex nonlinear relationships between predictors and outcomes and interactions among predictors (Auret & Aldrich, 2012). DT was implemented using the *fitctree* function in MATLAB with a cost function to penalise misclassification of the minority class, tuning of the hyperparameter *MinLeafSize* (the minimum number of leaf node observations, which controls the depth or complexity of the tree), and all other settings at default.

Support vector machine (SVM) is one of the most extensively used machine learning algorithms (Schölkopf et al., 2001, Schölkopf & Smola, 2002). The algorithm maps the input data into a high-dimensional feature space and constructs an optimal separating hyperplane that maximises the margin, which is the distance between the hyperplane and the nearest data points (support vectors) of each class of data in the space (Schölkopf et al., 2001, Schölkopf & Smola, 2002, Vapnik, 1999). The mapping is performed by a kernel function, which determines the smoothness and efficiency of class separation, the most common being the following: linear, radial basis function, polynomial, and sigmoid (Hsu et al., 2003). The SVM then makes predictions by assigning new points to one side of the hyperplane or the other. SVM was implemented using the *fitcsvm* function in MATLAB with a cost function to penalise misclassification of the minority class, tuning of the hyperparameters *BoxConstraint* (controls the maximum penalty imposed on margin-violating observations), and *KernelScale* (scaling parameter for the input data), and all other settings at default.

A neural network is a simplified model of the way the human brain processes information (Minsky & Papert, 1969). It works by simulating a large number of interconnected processing units (nodes) that resemble abstract versions of neurons (Abiodun et al., 2018, Sharkawy, 2020). The processing units are arranged in a layered structure that resembles the human brain. Input data are presented to the first layer, and values are propagated from each neuron to every neuron in the next layer with varying connection strengths (or weights) until a result (class) is delivered from the final output layer. NN was implemented using the *fitcnet* function in MATLAB to train a feedforward, fully connected neural network for classification, with inverse frequency observation weights, tuning of the hyperparameters *Activations* (activation functions for the fully connected layers of the model), *Lambda* (regularisation strength), *LayerWeightsInitializer* (function to initialise the fully connected layer weights), *LayerBiasesInitializer* (type of initial fully connected layer biases), *LayerSizes* (sizes of the fully connected layers), and all other settings as default.

Random forest (RF) is an ensemble machine learning algorithm that consists of many decision trees, where each tree is trained on bagged data (sampling with replacement) using a random selection of features (Breiman, 2001). In other words, each decision tree in the random forest is trained on a different subset of examples and features to introduce variation among trees. The main principle behind this method is that a group of ‘weak learners’ can work in tandem to form a ‘strong learner.’ The output of the random forest is the class selected by most trees. RF was implemented using the *fitcensemble* function in MATLAB with the *Method* set to *Bag*, with inverse frequency observation weights, tuning of the hyperparameters *NumLearningCycles* (number of trees in the forest), *MinLeafSize* (minimum observations per leaf), *SplitCriterion* (importance measure attributed to the splitting variable), and *NumVariablesToSample* (number

of features to select at random for each split in the tree). The hyperparameter *MaxNumSplits* (maximal number of decision splits per tree) was fixed at 20 to limit the growth of very deep (complex) trees and avoid overfitting, and all other settings were left at default values.

Random undersampling boosting (RUSBoost) is an ensemble classification algorithm designed to alleviate the class imbalance problem (Seiffert et al., 2009). It is a combination of the random undersampling method and an ensemble boosting classifier. First, RUSBoost undersamples the majority class data examples while drawing subsets from the dataset. Then, the ensemble boosting classifier is trained on the balanced subsets. Boosting works by learning a set of classifiers sequentially, where later classifiers focus on the mistakes of earlier classifiers and example weights are modified with the goal of correctly classifying examples in the next iteration (Freund & Schapire, 1997). Upon completion, all constructed models participate in a weighted vote to classify the examples. RUSBoost was implemented using the *fitensemble* function in MATLAB with decision tree base classifiers, the *Method* set to *RUSBoost*, tuning of the hyperparameters *NumLearningCycles*, *MinLeafSize*, *LearnRate* (determines the contribution of each base classifier to the final prediction and controls how quickly the algorithm converges), *SplitCriterion*, *NumVariablesToSample*, with *MaxNumSplits* set to 20.

2.4.3 Model fitting

Each algorithm contains parameters that are learned from the data and ‘hyperparameters’ that govern the learning process, whose value must be determined before learning commences. To fairly estimate the performance of the models on unseen data and not introduce biases in the choices of hyperparameters, a nested cross-validation (NCV) scheme was implemented. NCV is widely considered as the gold-standard approach for developing a predictive model and evaluating its performance, as it strictly controls the information leak between training and test

data and provides an unbiased estimate of generalisation accuracy to unseen data (Douglas et al. 2013; Japkowicz and Shah 2011; Krstajic et al. 2014; Misaki et al. 2010; Varma and Simon 2006). The procedure consisted of two nested k -fold cross-validation loops: an outer one to test generalisation accuracy to unseen data, and an inner one for optimisation of hyperparameters. The data was first partitioned into 10 nonoverlapping outer folds (subsets). Following a standard k -fold cross-validation approach, each fold was used once as the test set and the remaining $k-1$ folds (90% of the data) as the training set. For each iteration of the outer loop, the training set was partitioned into 10 folds to be used in the inner cross-validation loop, where hyperparameter tuning was performed using Bayesian optimisation. The hyperparameter values that gave the minimum cross-validation error in the inner loop were selected, and that model version was then retrained on the outer training set and its performance evaluated on the held-out test fold in the outer loop. This process was repeated 10 times so that each of the original 10 folds was used as the test set once and predictions were obtained for each entry in data set. Model performance on the outer test folds was assessed using the balanced accuracy (average accuracy on both classes) and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (a measure of a binary classifier's discrimination power, ranging from 0.5 for an uninformative model to 1 for perfect discrimination). It should be noted that the purpose of NCV is to provide an assessment of the entire model-building process and an estimate of the generalisation accuracy of each algorithm, but it is not used to produce the final version of a model. The best performing algorithm from the NCV was selected and tuned using a 'flat' 10-fold cross-validation with Bayesian optimisation (the inner loop procedure from the NCV), then retrained using the entire dataset to produce the 'finalised' model.

2.4.4 Model interpretation

Shapley values from cooperative game theory were used to interpret the output of the best-performing (finalised) machine learning model. Shapley values assign an attribution to features on a per-sample basis, based on how they contribute to the prediction (Lundberg et al., 2020). This information is useful for understanding how a model makes decisions and for identifying which features are most important for making accurate predictions. In short, the final contribution of an input feature is determined as the average of its contributions in all possible permutations of the feature set. The full treatment of how Shapley values are formulated is available at (Molnar, 2020). Shapley values have become the state-of-the-art explanation method for black-box machine learning models due to their strong theoretical foundations and distinct advantages over other traditional methods, such as clear interpretation, easy implementation, and applicability to any type of data (Cha et al., 2021, Linardatos et al., 2020, Razavi et al., 2021, Molnar, 2020). In addition, Shapley values provide global as well as local explanations, that is, they provide explanations that summarise the entire dataset as well as individual observations. A global feature importance plot was generated by averaging the absolute Shapley values for every feature across all observations (grid cells) and sorting them in decreasing importance. A local explanation summary plot (beeswarm or distribution plot) of the association between the observation-level Shapley values and the observed scores for a given feature was used to describe the dominant direction of association between feature and outcome. Shapley values were implemented using the *shapley* command in MATLAB with *Method* set to *interventional*.

3. Results

3.1 Incidence statistics

The total number of seed potato crops planted in Scotland was relatively consistent among years (mean 4675, SD 206; range 4408-5019) (Figure 1a). Virus infections were confirmed in 5727 (8.8%) of all the crops inspected over the study period, with marked variation among years (SD 4.7%; range 3.67-16.3%). The annual percentage of infected crops showed an upward trend in FG2 to FG7 from 2017 to 2020, then a decrease in most field generations over the final two years (Figure 1a). The 65,450 seed potato lots in the SSPCS dataset were comprised of 18,648 pre-basic crops (FG1 to FG4) and 46,802 basic crops (FG5 to FG7), with a ratio of 17.1 for the number of infected basic to pre-basic crops over the study period, and high variation in the infection ratio among years (SD 9; range 8.1-38.2). Disease severity levels were low in all infected crops, with a median value across all growing crop inspections of 0.01% (IQR 0.002-0.02%) for infected pre-basic crops and 0.02% (IQR 0.01-0.05%) for infected basic crops. PVY was the most prevalent virus overall in single and mixed infections ($n = 4077$; mean frequency across years 63.2%, SD 8.4%; range 49.6-74.4%), followed by PLRV ($n = 1103$; mean frequency across years 13.7%, SD 12.1%; range 0.8-39.4%), and PVA ($n = 516$, mean frequency across years 9.4%, SD 5.2%; range 1.9-20.5%) (Figure 1b). Notably, PVY has been decreasing from 2019-2022, while incidence of PLRV has increased six-fold over the same period, from 47 crops in 2019 to 289 crops in 2022.

There was a total of 476 different potato varieties in the data, of which 253 were infected, with Maris Piper having the highest incidence of PVY (11.7%) and PLRV infection (5.3%), and Desiree the highest incidence of PVA (4.2%) (Figure 1c). Eight of the 10 most infected varieties were also in the top 10 most cultivated varieties, except for Valor and Charlotte, ranked 16th and 12th, respectively. Of the 5727 infected crops, 5093 were single virus infections, 593 were double, 38 were triple and 3 were quadruple infections, with mixed infections occurring in 43

different combinations of the 10 viruses tested (Table 1). Of the 55 possible species pair combinations (ten potato viruses and potato blackleg), 32 pairs were removed from the co-occurrence analysis due to insufficient co-occurrence data (Figure 1d). Among the viruses, there were 12 positive co-occurrences ($p < 0.005$) and no negative co-occurrences. Potato blackleg was positively associated with eight potato viruses ($p < 0.005$), with no negative co-occurrences.

3.2 Spatial and spatiotemporal patterns of disease

Seed potato production was heavily concentrated in the northern (Inverness, Aberdeenshire) and central (Perth and Kinross, Angus) regions of the eastern seaboard of Scotland, with pockets of production in the southern Borders region (Figure 2). The spatial distribution of PVY and PVA incidence closely matched the distribution of seed potato crops, whereas PLRV was relatively more limited in southern production regions (Figure 3). This was confirmed by the Directional Distribution and Central Feature analyses, which showed that the directional pattern of PVY, PLRV, and PVA incidence all followed a north-northeast distribution, but the spatial mean centre of the PLRV distribution was 7.75 km further north than that of the PVA distribution, and 24.65 km further north than the mean centre of the PVY distribution (Figure 4).

The Optimised Hot Spot Analysis of virus incidence rates (IRW) revealed that out of a total of 549 grid cells containing both potato and viruses, there were 163 hot spots and 258 cold spots of PVY, 153 hot spots and 239 cold spots of PLRV, and 74 hot spots of PVA (Figure 5). Hot spots were concentrated in a central intense cluster, indicating an area where the three viruses were significantly more problematic, whereas cold spots were concentrated in large clusters in the north and south of the country, indicating areas where the viruses were less problematic. The Optimised Outlier Analysis provided additional insight on these patterns, identifying a total of 36 high outlier and 66 low outlier locations for PVY, 21 high and 71 low outlier locations for

PLRV, and 1 high and 18 low outlier locations for PVA (Figure 6). Outliers of high incidence rates were scattered sporadically throughout the north and south of the country, whereas outliers of low incidence rates were found around the edges of the central clusters of high IRW for all three viruses.

The emerging Hot Spot Analysis revealed striking differences in temporal trends of hot- and cold-spot patterns of incidence rates among the three viruses (Figure 7; Table 2). The intensively cropped central production region previously identified as a hot spot of disease for all three viruses (Figure 5) was dominated by a large, contiguous cluster of 48 persistent hot spots of PVY, indicating that this was a consistently problematic area over time. Conversely, there was a large contiguous cluster of 48 persistent cold spots of PVY in the north of the country (Inverness), denoting a constant trend of low incidence rates, where PVY was relatively uncommon. In contrast, most seed-producing areas were covered by sporadic hot spots of PLRV, signifying that incidence rates were variable in space and time, with an on-again off-again pattern of hot spots (Figure 7b). Similar to PVY, there was a large cluster of persistent, consecutive, and oscillating cold spots in the north of the country. There were 10 new hot spots of PLRV scattered in the north and south of the country, indicating regions where PLRV has been increasing in the final year of the study. There were no spatiotemporal patterns detected for PVA for most of the country, except for six consecutive hot spots in the north-east (Figure 7c). A 3D visualisation of the hot and cold spots for each location and year revealed an interesting phenomenon in the north-east of the country (Aberdeenshire); there was a widespread area that became first-time hot spots of PVY infection in 2019 and 2020, which then disappeared to become first-time hot spots of PLRV infection in the following two years (Figure 7d,e). Analysis of clusters and outliers in both space and time via the Local Outlier Analysis showed that areas

of intense crop production were fringed by locations where the only statistically significant type of pattern throughout time were low clusters and low outliers for all three viruses (Figure 8a-c). There were large areas identified as having multiple types of cluster and outlier categories throughout time for PVY and PLRV (Figure 8a,b), but further analysis of individual years revealed that many such locations in intensively cropped regions were high clusters in many years, and these contiguous areas of high incidence rates tended to be bordered by low clusters and low outliers in many years. For PVA, low outliers accounted for 54% of grid cells with a significant pattern (Figure 8c,f), signifying lower incidence rates than expected, which is consistent with the gradual, overall decline of PVA over the study period (Figure 1b).

3.3 Predictors of disease

Annual gridded PVY incidence data were analysed using a suite of seven machine learning algorithms to quantify the importance of 54 crop, mother crop (seed stock), field, neighbour (number and density of surrounding seed and ware potato crops), bioclimatic, and soil features as predictors of PVY incidence in space and time (Figure 9). RF was the best performing algorithm and was able to classify PVY incidence with a an AUROC of 0.83 (SD=0.027) under the 10 x 10-fold nested cross-validation procedure, giving confidence in the results of the feature importance analysis (Table 3). The optimised hyperparameters of the finalised model were: *NumLearningCycles* = 112, *MinLeafSize* = 2, *SplitCriterion* = *gdi*, and *NumVariablesToSample* = 7. The finalised model was interpreted by computing Shapley values on the out-of-bag samples not used to develop the trees, thereby explaining the relative importance of each feature to predictions of the finalised model on unseen data (Figure 10; Supplementary Table 2). Notably, the features that had the highest importance values were the presence of PVY in the mother crop, presence of potato blackleg in the crop and mother crop, presence of rogues in the crop and pre-

roguing in the mother crop, and varietal resistance to PVY (Figure 10a). High values of the first five of these features were associated with prediction of incidence, whereas high varietal resistance scores were associated with prediction of healthy crops (Figure 10b). We picked the four individual features with the highest importance that could be known in advance of a growing season (presence of PVY in the mother crop, pre-roguing in the mother crop, presence of blackleg in the mother crop, and varietal resistance to PVY) and trained, tuned, and tested another Random Forest (RF2). Despite using only four features, RF2 still achieved an AUROC of 0.76 (SD=0.032) under the NCV procedure (Table 3). The optimised hyperparameters of the finalised RF2 model were: *NumLearningCycles* = 20, *MinLeafSize* = 44, *SplitCriterion* = *gdi*, and *NumVariablesToSample* = 2, indicating a simpler model than RF.

4. Discussion

This study provides three key advances in our understanding of the landscape epidemiology of potato viruses in Scotland. First, we analysed temporal patterns of disease to provide an overview of annual incidence levels, changes to species composition, variety-specific incidence, and species co-occurrences. Second, we used ArcGIS to identify large-scale spatial and spatiotemporal patterns of incidence, revealing differences in the distribution of the three predominant virus species (PVY, PLRV, PVA) and identifying problematic areas. Third, we used a machine learning approach to gain a deeper understanding of risk factors for PVY incidence at the landscape-scale and provide accurate predictive models that can be used by researchers and practitioners. The new knowledge gained leads to several recommendations for management of potato viruses and future research efforts.

The virus health of Scottish seed potatoes is a unique selling point in the UK and worldwide, and the results of this study confirm that virus incidence and disease severity remain low overall, particularly in high-grade pre-basic crops, but with an upsurge from 2018 onwards. The potato industry lost two important active ingredients for controlling aphids in 2018 and 2019, the neonicotinoid thiamethoxam was withdrawn by the European Commission in 2018, and the pyridine azomethine derivative pymetrozine followed in 2019. It is possible the loss of these aphicides is linked to the increase in virus incidence and will likely make management of insecticide resistance more challenging going forward. This time-period also saw a shift in virus species composition towards increased PLRV and decreased PVY and PVA (Figure 1a,b), with a striking localised geographic example (Figure 7d,e). Previous research has shown that changes in PLRV incidence are strongly linked to the abundance of the peach potato aphid (*Myzus persicae*) in the preceding year, with milder winters allowing increased survival of vector aphids and earlier build up and migration of populations (Pickup et al., 2009). Much of the spread of PLRV occurs early in the season in May to early July, and thus an early spread of *M. persicae* can lead to an increase in incidence (Khurana & Garg, 2003). Transmission of PLRV is also temperature dependent (Chung et al., 2016), and in the last five years of the study period winters have been notably milder than average in Eastern Scotland, except for 2021 (<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/climate>). This too may account for the recent upsurge in overall incidence levels. Mixed infections, which can be problematic, accounted for 11.1% of total incidence over the study period. For example, mixed infection of PVX and PVY (0.75% of total incidence), or either or both of them with PLRV or PVA (4.8% of total incidence), produces much more severe symptoms than separate infection of each (German, 2001, He et al., 2014, Kreuze et al., 2020, MacLachlan et al., 1954).

The ArcGIS analyses revealed that the hot spots of infection for potato viruses in Scotland were clustered in the intensively cropped central production regions of Perth & Kinross and Angus, indicating a large geographic area where potato viruses could be better managed, or conditions are more favourable for aphid vectors and/or disease development (Figure 5); notably, this is a large area of intense ware production and low-grade basic seed. Interestingly, these large contiguous clusters of hot spots were bordered by low outliers of incidence rates in space and time, suggesting that risk of infection decreases with distance away from densely cropped areas (Figures 6,8). This is not unexpected for aphid-transmitted viruses, but to our knowledge this is the first time this phenomenon has been quantified at a landscape-scale. PVY is particularly problematic in the Angus region, which was covered by a large, contiguous cluster of persistent hot spots, meaning that incidence rates were higher than average for over 90% of the study period (Figure 7a). Conversely, there were large clusters of persistent cold spots of PVY and PLRV in the heavily cropped region around Inverness in the north of the country, meaning incidence rates were lower than average for over 90% of the study period. This pinpoints a large geographic area where the majority of crops grown are high-grade pre-basic crops. There is a nil tolerance for PVY/PLRV/PVA in pre-basic crops under the SSPCS, therefore crops are better managed and there is less primary inoculum for virus vectors in this region. The 3D visualisation of spatiotemporal patterns of hot and cold spots revealed a very interesting phenomenon the north-eastern production region of Aberdeenshire, where there has been a widespread change in incidence between PVY and PLRV in recent years (Figure 7d,e), which accounted for much of the observed increase in PLRV in the final years of the study period (Figure 1b). This cannot be readily explained by a change in varieties grown, as the most cultivated varieties and their frequency was very similar from 2020-2022 in this area (data not shown). It is more likely

related to the aforementioned milder winters and withdrawal of important aphicides in the final years of the study period. To gain a deeper understanding of the drivers of these observed patterns of disease, we can examine the results of the interpretable machine learning analysis of PVY, which was the most prevalent virus overall.

To our knowledge, the Shapley feature importance analysis of RF provides the first assessment of a comprehensive range of crop, mother crop (seed stock), crop distribution, topography, soil, and weather risk factors for PVY at a national scale (Figure 10). Several of the most important features for prediction of PVY incidence were related to the health status of the mother crop, highlighting the significance of seed input as a major source of primary PVY inoculum for virus vectors in Scotland, and providing a clear framing of the purpose of seed schemes around the world, which aim to assure the quality of marketed seed through inspection and various sanitation and disease avoidance measures, such as limiting the number of field generations. Conversely, volunteer plants in crops and mother crops were of negligible importance, suggesting a much more limited role as reservoirs of inoculum and drivers of PVY outbreaks at the landscape-scale, although no data were available on volunteers in surrounding non-potato crops. This is in contrast to the results of a similar study on the landscape epidemiology of potato blackleg, where volunteers in potato crops were highly predictive of blackleg outbreaks (Skelsey et al., 2023). However, distance to both the nearest neighbouring seed and ware crop had relatively high importance values, indicating cross-contamination between diseased and healthy crops, which serves to corroborate the ArcGIS OOA (Figure 6) and LOA (Figure 8) results showing an association between distribution of incidence rates in space and time and proximity to dense areas of potato production. Similarly, the high importance of blackleg infection in the crop and mother crop as predictors of PVY (with high feature values being predictive of

incidence) serves to corroborate the results of the co-occurrence analysis, which identified a statistically significant positive association between blackleg and eight different potato viruses at the landscape-scale, including PVY (Figure 1d). This is most likely related to a build-up of blackleg together with viruses over successive field generations, as indicated by the importance of field generation as a predictor, with higher values predicting incidence. It is possible that insect vectors are transmitting some of these pathogens together, as a wide range of species are known to carry potato viruses (Lacomme et al., 2017) and blackleg pathogens (Rossmann et al., 2018), but such a phenomenon has yet to be confirmed. High values of pre-roguing and roguing of symptomatic plants in crops and mother crops were also informative predictors of PVY incidence, highlighting that visual observation and removal of diseased plants is a challenging task, as infection can be asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic depending on the PVY isolate / potato cultivar combination (Davie, 2014, Lacomme et al., 2017, Ravnkar, 2005). High varietal resistance scores to PVY were predictive of healthy crops, which was unexpected as the number of potato varieties expressing broad-spectrum resistance to all strains of PVY is low (Valkonen et al., 2017). This may be because the seed certification scheme is able to consistently supply growers with sufficiently healthy seed to limit the potential losses caused by PVY in susceptible interactions. Crop location was an important predictor, with lower values of the northing grid coordinate (i.e., more southerly crops) and higher values of the easting grid coordinate being predictive of incidence. Seed production in Scotland enjoys a natural advantage due to the northerly location, as aphids generally migrate into crops later in the growing season several weeks after crop emergence when plants have developed some resistance to virus systemic movement, known as mature plant resistance (Barker & Dale, 2006). Accordingly, temperature features were important predictors, with higher values predicting incidence, most likely due to

warmer winters leading to an earlier start to the aphid flight season. It is plausible that the importance of temperature partly explains the observed cluster of cold spots of incidence rates in the cooler, northernmost production locations, together with the more widespread planting of high grade pre-basic crops (Figure 7a). Interestingly, high wind gusts during the warmest quarter of the year were predictive of incidence, possibly due to wind-assisted passive dispersal to more distant crops. Finally, several soil variables were informative predictors, with high values of clay and silt in soils being predictive of incidence, as well as a low C:N ratio. This is likely an indicator of an impact of soil quality on overall crop health, and highlights the importance of maintaining soil health for the regulation of insect pests and vectors in potato production (Alyokhin et al., 2020).

The AUROC of the RF classifier is considered excellent (Hosmer Jr et al., 2013); therefore, our study provides a new tool for discriminating between low- and high-risk areas of PVY at the landscape-scale. While employing only four features (presence of PVY in the mother crop, pre-roguing in the mother crop, presence of blackleg in the mother crop, and varietal resistance to PVY) for classification slightly lowered predictive performance, the simple version of the classifier (RF2) may be more suitable for development as a decision support tool in the potato industry. Concretely, within a seed certification scheme, these four features are known in advance of a growing season, therefore RF2 could be used to forecast high risk areas prior to crop emergence, so that stricter monitoring and control / disease avoidance measures could be implemented. Nevertheless, it is likely that predictive performance of both model versions could be improved. Although the focus of the current study was in using information on crops and their surrounding environment to gain additional insights into potato virus epidemiology, it is possible that inclusion of new features related to aphid population dynamics could be beneficial. For

example, in the UK aphid vector pressure is calculated by summing the total catch of each aphid species from the Rothamsted Research / SASA network of suction traps (<https://insectsurvey.com/>), after multiplication by a factor estimating the efficiency of that species as a vector of PVY. It would be of interest in a future study to investigate if new features related to the aphid pressure each season improves the performance of RF, and if aphid pressure from the previous season, potentially combined with existing features on the following winter and spring temperatures, leads to significant improvements in the ability of RF2 to forecast high risk areas ahead of the upcoming growing season. However, there are only four suction traps to cover Scotland, therefore the spatial resolution of the data will be coarse compared to the other features used and may be insufficient for this purpose. In addition, the default threshold of 0.5 for interpreting probabilities to binary class labels was used in all models, and it is possible that an analysis of different thresholds may identify an optimal value for improving predictive performance (e.g., Skelsey et al., 2018).

The results of this study lead to several recommendations for improved management of potato viruses in Scotland. We advise that the potato virus frequency chart (Figure 1b) is reproduced each year to keep track of virus population shifts and for comparison with aphid species and flight activity data from the suction trap network. The EHSA and 3D visualisation of the underlying space-time hot and cold spot results are also particularly useful (Figure 7), as they can be used on an ongoing basis each year to identify hot spots of infection that may produce high-virus seed, and persistently problematic areas where it may be beneficial to introduce tighter control measures, such as earlier or increased spraying of mineral oils and/or insecticides (Al-Mrabe et al., 2010), straw mulching (Kirchner et al., 2014, Saucke & Döring, 2004), or increased rates of post-harvest tuber testing. The resulting maps also empower grower decision-

making with regards to planting locations and varietal choices when such decisions are possible. In particular, the 3D visualisations of the space-time hot spot analysis (Figure 7d-f) can be used to pinpoint the geographic locations where virus populations are changing over time, alerting growers to be vigilant for different symptoms or cultivar choices and indicating areas of interest for further scientific investigation into the driving forces behind population shifts. Maps of seed potato distribution (Figure 2) and clusters of high virus incidence rates (Figures 6-8) also provide useful information to optimise the configuration of the national suction trap network; for example, there is currently a trap located in Ayr where there is limited seed potato production. Relocation or addition of new traps to areas of high incidence rates could be beneficial as decision support systems for potato farmers in the UK are centred around aphid monitoring, using the national suction-trap network for a regional indication of flight activity, and in-field water-traps for a local indication as a paid service provided by Fera Science and the Agricultural and Horticulture Development Board. In addition, forecasts of the date of the first aphid flights and abundance in spring and early summer are made in the UK using long-term suction-trap network and weather data (Zhou et al., 1995). The results of the machine learning analyses demonstrated that PVY incidence can be accurately forecast without reference to aphid data, using information on crops and their surrounding environment, and as discussed above, it is anticipated that the addition of new features related to aphid pressure could lead to an improved decision support tool for the industry that can forecast virus incidence at a finer spatial resolution than the current regional scale for aphid forecasts. Interpretation of the classification model highlighted the problem of identifying and removing infected plants, as symptoms may not be obvious, but several rapid, non-destructive, and accurate techniques for detection of PVY in potato have been developed using hyperspectral imaging coupled with advanced machine

learning methods, and it is possible these technologies could assist with the human resource-intensive activities of crop inspection and roguing (Griffel et al., 2018, Mahlein et al., 2018, Moslemkhani et al., 2019). An excellent review of the state-of-the-art in this burgeoning field is given by Mahlein et al. (2018). The model interpretation analysis also revealed that distance to both the nearest neighbouring seed and ware crop were important predictors of disease, therefore it may be beneficial to revise the required crop separation distances under the SSPCS; currently, these are set at 2 drill widths where crops are drilled in the same direction, or else three metres (SASA, 2022). Field generation was also flagged as an important driving factor, and currently the SSPCS sets a zero-tolerance limit for PVY, PVA, and PLRV in crops up to the 4th field generation. It would be an interesting exercise to investigate the effects of extending this to the 5th field generation to assess potential reductions in seedborne infection and sources of primary inoculum. Finally, the importance of northing and easting as drivers of incidence suggests potential for the design of disease suppressive landscapes, where a strategic approach to the introduction of new potato production areas is adopted. For example, a shift in potato production from the semi-arid east to rain-fed production in the west and north may become a viable option to maintain the virus health of Scottish seed potatoes in the future as the climate warms.

In conclusion, this paper provides new information on the landscape epidemiology of potato viruses. Our study has several strengths, including the size of the dataset, its spatial and temporal coverage, and the innovative blend of ArcGIS and diverse machine learning techniques used for analysis. The results provide the first evidence of statistically significant species co-occurrences and national-scale patterns of incidence rates in space and time, and the first comprehensive analysis of risk factors at the landscape-scale in Scotland. The findings led to new suggestions for improved virus management and future research endeavours, and the models produced can be

used as research or decision support tools. The methodology developed in this study is extendable to data from other seed potato certification schemes or any geo-referenced crop disease or pest datasets.

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Conflict of interest statement

None of the authors have present or potential conflicts of interest, nor financial, personal, or other relationships with other persons or organisations that might inappropriately influence or be perceived to influence their work.

Data availability

The virus resistance scores for potato varieties are publicly available from the Potato Variety Database (<https://potatoes.agricrops.org/>). Terrain variables were extracted from high resolution digital terrain models (DTM) (available at <https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/>). Soil variables were derived from digital maps provided by Scotland's Soils (available at <https://soils.environment.gov.scot/>). The potato virus data from the Scottish Seed Potato Classification Scheme are subject to a data sharing agreement between the author and SASA, and the weather data used to generate bioclimatic variables are subject to a data sharing agreement between the author and the United Kingdom Meteorological Office, and under these terms may not be made publicly available. The MATLAB R2023a code for training, tuning,

testing, and interpreting the machine learning models is available from

<https://github.com/pskelsey/potatoVirusMachineLearning>.

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Supporting Information

Supplementary Table 1. Integrated dataset used for analysis of predictors of potato virus Y incidence.

Supplementary Table 2. Shapley values of the features used in the random forest classifier for prediction of potato virus Y incidence in space and time.

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Figure 1. Seed potato production and incidence of potato viruses in Scotland. **(a)** Total number of seed potato crops planted each year and percentage infected with potato viruses in field generations FG1 to FG7. **(b)** Frequency of potato virus species. **(c)** Heat map showing variety-specific incidence for the top ten most infected potato varieties, ranked from highest to lowest. Numbers in grid cells are the number of crops infected for a specific virus (single or mixed infections), and the row numbers to the right of the heat map are the total number of crops of that variety in the dataset, with their ranking for most cultivated in parentheses. **(d)** Heat map showing statistically significant positive and negative species associations. Species names are positioned to indicate the columns and rows that represent their pairwise relationships with other species.

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of seed potato crops. Total number of seed potato crops planted during 2009-2022.

Figure 3. Geographic distribution of potato virus incidence in Scotland during 2009-2022. Total number of seed potato crops infected with (a) potato virus Y, (b) potato leaf roll virus, and (c) potato virus A.

Figure 4. Directional distribution of potato virus incidence in Scotland. The results show a standard deviational ellipse (revealing directional trend and dispersion) and central tendency for incidence of potato virus Y, potato leaf roll virus, and potato virus A during 2009-2022.

Figure 5. Spatial patterns of potato virus incidence rates in Scotland. Output from the Optimised Hot Spot Analysis of potato virus incidence rates during the period 2009-2022, for **(a)** potato virus Y, **(b)** potato leaf roll virus, and **(c)** potato virus A. Warm colours indicate spatial clusters of high values of incidence (hot spots), and cool colours indicate spatial clusters of low values of incidence (cold spots). Percentages represent confidence level.

Figure 6. Spatial outliers of potato virus incidence rates in Scotland. Output from the Optimised Outlier Analysis of potato virus incidence rates during the period 2009-2022, for (a) potato virus Y, (b) potato leaf roll virus, and (c) potato virus A. The maps show hot spots (High-High clusters), cold spots (Low-Low clusters), high spatial outliers (High-Low clusters) and low spatial outliers (Low-High clusters) of incidence.

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Figure 7. Spatiotemporal patterns of potato virus incidence rates in Scotland. Output from the Emerging Hot Spot Analysis of potato virus incidence rates showing hot and cold spot trends during the period 2009-2022, for **(a)** potato virus Y, **(b)** potato leaf roll virus, and **(c)** potato virus A. The bottom row shows a 3D visualisation of the hot and cold spot results for each location and year in the bounded area of the first panel, for **(d)** potato virus Y, **(e)** potato leaf roll virus, and **(f)** potato virus A.

Figure 8. Spatiotemporal patterns of clusters and outliers in potato virus incidence rates in Scotland. Output from the Local Outlier Analysis of potato blackleg incidence rates during the period 2009-2022, for **(a)** potato virus Y, **(b)** potato leaf roll virus, and **(c)** potato virus A. The map shows locations where the only statistically significant type of pattern throughout time were hot spots (High-High clusters), cold spots (Low-Low clusters), high outliers (High-Low clusters) and low outliers (Low-High clusters) of incidence throughout time, and locations where there have been multiple types of statistically significant cluster and outlier categories throughout time. The bottom row shows a 3D visualisation of the results for each location and year in the bounded area of the first panel, for **(d)** potato virus Y, **(e)** potato leaf roll virus, and **(f)** potato virus A.

Figure 9. Annual gridded patterns of the binary response variable (presence/absence of potato virus Y) in the machine learning analysis of predictors of potato virus Y in space and time.

Figure 10. Interpretation plots for the random forest classifier for potato virus Y incidence. The left-hand panel is a global feature importance plot that presents features in descending order based on their overall importance on the model's outcomes, where each bar is the mean of absolute Shapley values across all samples (grid cells). Results for the 20 most important features are shown. The right-hand panel is a local explanation summary plot that combines feature importance with feature effects, and shows the direction of the relationship between a feature and the model outcome on a per-sample basis, where the colour corresponds to feature value. The higher the Shapley value, the more the feature is predictive for incidence, and the lower the Shapley value, the more the feature is predictive for absence of disease.

Table 1. Incidence of potato viruses in single and mixed infections in the Scottish Seed Potato Classification Scheme dataset, 2009-2022.

Number of infected seed lots and % of all infections*							
Single infection		Double infection		Triple infection		Quadruple infection	
PVY	3549 (61.97)	PVY-PLRV	285 (4.98)	PVY-PVA-PMTV	7 (0.12)	PVY-PVA-PLRV-PVV	2 (0.03)
PLRV	767 (13.39)	PVY-PVA	89 (1.55)	PVY-PVA-PVV	7 (0.12)	PVY-PVA-PVX-PVV	1 (0.02)
PVA	331 (5.78)	PVY-PMTV	62 (1.08)	PVY-PLRV-PVX	5 (0.09)		
PMTV	202 (3.53)	PVY-PVX	37 (0.65)	PVY-PLRV-PMTV	3 (0.05)		
PVX	155 (2.71)	PVA-PVX	32 (0.56)	PVY-PVA-PLRV	3 (0.05)		
TRV	51 (0.89)	PVA-PVV	17 (0.30)	PVY-PLRV-TBRV	2 (0.03)		
PVV	31 (0.54)	PLRV-PMTV	11 (0.19)	PVY-PVA-PVX	2 (0.05)		
TBRV	5 (0.09)	PVA-PLRV	11 (0.19)	PLRV-PVX-PMTV	1 (0.02)		
PVS	2 (0.03)	PVA-PMTV	10 (0.17)	PVA-PLRV-PMTV	1 (0.02)		
		PVY-PVV	10 (0.17)	PVA-PLRV-PVV	1 (0.02)		
		PLRV-PVX	6 (0.10)	PVA-PLRV-PVX	1 (0.02)		
		PVX-PMTV	4 (0.07)	PVY-PLRV-PVV	1 (0.02)		
		PMTV-TRV	3 (0.05)	PVY-PMTV-PVS	1 (0.02)		
		PVY-PVS	3 (0.05)	PVY-PMTV-TRV	1 (0.02)		
		PVY-TRV	3 (0.05)	PVY-PVX-PMTV	1 (0.02)		
		PLRV-PVS	1 (0.02)	PVY-PVX-PVS	1 (0.02)		
		PLRV-PVV	1 (0.02)				
		PLRV-TRV	1 (0.02)				
		PMTV-PVS	1 (0.02)				
		PVA-TRV	1 (0.02)				
		PVX-PVM	1 (0.02)				
		PVX-PVV	1 (0.02)				
		PVX-TRV	1 (0.02)				
		PVY-PVM	1 (0.02)				
		PVY-TBRV	1 (0.02)				

* Virus infections were confirmed in 5727 of the 65,450 seed lots inspected over the study period. Numbers in parentheses are percentage infection rates in confirmed samples.

Table 2. Temporal trends in spatial patterns of hot and cold spots of potato virus incidence rates in Scotland, 2009-2022.

Trend*	Potato virus Y		Potato leaf roll virus		Potato virus A	
	Hot	Cold	Hot	Cold	Hot	Cold
New	0	0	10	0	0	0
Consecutive	8	0	1	17	6	0
Persistent	48	48	0	15	0	0
Sporadic	75	17	0	39	0	0
Oscillating	86	0	323	0	0	0

* New = statistically significant in the most recent time-step only, consecutive = statistically significant in the two final time-steps only, intensifying = statistically significant for 90% of time-steps and the intensity of clustering (of either low or high values) is increasing over time, persistent = statistically significant for 90% of time-steps with no discernible trend in the intensity of clustering over time, sporadic = statistically significant for the final time-step with a history of an on-again off-again pattern, oscillating = statistically significant for the final time-step with a history of being both hot and cold, historical = not statistically significant for the final time-step but has been for at least 90% of time-steps.

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Table 3. Nested 10-fold cross-validation performance metrics for predicting annual patterns of gridded potato virus Y incidence.

Model	Train		Test	
	Bal. acc.	AUROC	Bal. acc.	AUROC
DA	73% (1.2%)	0.82 (0.007)	70% (3.1%)	0.79 (0.028)
KNN	74% (0.1%)	0.81 (0.010)	71% (2.3%)	0.78 (0.031)
DT	72% (0.2%)	0.76 (0.024)	69% (2.2%)	0.74 (0.033)
SVM	71% (0.1%)	0.81 (0.004)	71% (3.4%)	0.79 (0.029)
NN	75% (0.2%)	0.83 (0.019)	72% (3.1%)	0.80 (0.028)
RF	78% (0.1%)	0.87 (0.008)	74% (3.6%)	0.83 (0.027)
RUSBoost	80% (0.1%)	0.89 (0.004)	73% (2.5%)	0.80 (0.024)
RF2	71% (0.5%)	0.79 (0.005)	70% (3.1%)	0.76 (0.032)

Bal. acc = balanced accuracy, AUROC = area under the receiver operating characteristics curve, DA = discriminant analysis, KNN = k -nearest neighbour, DT = decision tree, SVM = support vector machine, NN = neural network, RF = random forest, RUSBoost = random undersampling boosting, RF2 = random forest using only four features. Metrics are the average over training or test folds and standard deviations are given in parentheses.

Supplementary Table 1: Integrated dataset used for analysis of predictors of potato virus Y incidence.

Feature subset	Feature name	Description
Crop	PVY incidence	Response variable: a crop is diseased if symptoms found on any plant during any inspection [0,1]
	Planting DOY	Day of year crop was planted [1,365]
	Pre-basic	Seed category [0,1]
	Field generation	Number of field production generations after nuclear seed (no.)
	Varietal resistance	Score of 1 (low)-9 (high) resistance: scores for PVY ^O and PVY ^N were combined [0,1]
	Irrigated	Undesirable plants removed before inspection (%)
	Pre-roguing	Undesirable plants found during inspection (%)
	Rogues	Off-types of the same variety (%)
	Variations	Plants that grow from unharvested tubers (%)
	Volunteers	Same trait as the crop subset feature
	Mother crop	Irrigated mother crop
Pre-roguing in mother crop		Same health trait as the crop subset feature
Rogues in mother crop		Same health trait as the crop subset feature
Variations in mother crop		Same health trait as the crop subset feature
Volunteers in mother crop		Same health trait as the crop subset feature
Potato blackleg in mother crop		Same health trait as the crop subset feature
PVY in mother crop		Same health trait as the crop subset feature
Field	Northing	British National Grid coordinate (m)
	Easting	British National Grid coordinate (m)
	Field area	Size of inspected seed lot (ha)
	Slope	(deg.)
	Aspect	(deg.)
	Elevation	(m)
	Potato distribution	Distance to nearest seed crop
Total number of ware crops		(no.)
Total area of ware crops		(ha)
Distance to nearest ware crop		(m)
Bioclimatic	Annual mean temperature	(°C)
	Mean diurnal temperature range	(°C)
	Temperature seasonality	Standard deviation of mean monthly temperatures
	Max. temperature WM	(°C)
	Min. temperature CM	(°C)
	Temperature annual range	(°C)
	Isothermality	Ratio of mean diurnal temperature range to annual range (%)
	Mean temperature WSQ	(°C)
	Mean temperature DQ	(°C)
	Mean temperature WQ	(°C)
	Mean temperature CQ	(°C)
	Annual precipitation	(mm)
	Precipitation WSM	(mm)

Supplementary Table 1 continued:

Feature subset	Feature name	Description
	Precipitation DM	(mm)
	Precipitation seasonality	Ratio of the standard deviation of monthly precipitation to the mean monthly precipitation (%)
	Precipitation WSQ	(mm)
	Precipitation DQ	(mm)
	Precipitation WQ	(mm)
	Precipitation CQ	(mm)
	Annual median wind speed	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind speed WSQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind speed DQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind speed WQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind speed CQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Annual median wind gust	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind gust WSQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind gust DQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind gust WQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Median wind gust CQ	(m s ⁻¹)
	Annual hours of high (≥90%) RH	(no.)
	Hours of high RH WSQ	(no.)
	Hours of high RH DQ	(no.)
	Hours of high RH WQ	(no.)
	Hours of high RH CQ	(no.)
Soil	Available water capacity	(mm)
	pH	(-)
	Total organic C	(%)
	Loss on ignition	(%)
	Carbon	(%)
	Nitrogen	(%)
	C:N ratio	(-)
	Sand percentage	(%)
	Silt percentage	(%)
	Clay percentage	(%)
	Exchangeable Ca	(mEq per 100 g air-dried soil)
	Exchangeable Mg	(mEq per 100 g air-dried soil)
	Exchangeable Na	(mEq per 100 g air-dried soil)
	Exchangeable K	(mEq per 100 g air-dried soil)
	Exchangeable H	(mEq per 100 g air-dried soil)
	Sum of cations	(mEq per 100 g air-dried soil)
	Base saturation	(%)
	Total P ₂ O ₅	(mq per 100 g air-dried soil)

WM = warmest month, CM = coldest month, DM = driest month, WSM = wettest month, WQ = warmest quarter, CQ = coldest quarter, DQ = driest quarter, WSQ = wettest quarter, RH = relative humidity.

Supplementary Table 2: Shapley values of the features used in the random forest classifier for prediction of potato virus Y incidence in space and time.

Feature	Importance	Feature	Importance
PVY in mother crop	0.0970	Mean diurnal temperature range	0.0097
Blackleg	0.0840	Annual median wind gust	0.0096
Rogues	0.0578	Loss on ignition	0.0095
Blackleg in mother crop	0.0524	Total organic C	0.0094
Pre-roguing in mother crop	0.0454	Exchangeable K	0.0094
Resistance to PVY	0.0328	Mean temperature DQ	0.0093
Northing	0.0316	Precipitation seasonality	0.0093
Annual mean temperature	0.0286	Precipitation WQ	0.0092
Temperature seasonality	0.0265	Slope	0.0092
Easting	0.0241	Aspect	0.0091
Rogues in mother crop	0.0210	Exchangeable Mg	0.0092
Distance to nearest seed crop	0.0198	Precipitation DQ	0.0090
Clay percentage	0.0165	Elevation	0.0090
Pre-roguing	0.0154	Exchangeable Ca	0.0089
Field generation	0.0152	Available water capacity	0.0088
Distance to nearest ware crop	0.0143	Annual precipitation	0.0088
C:N ratio	0.0131	Precipitation DM	0.0088
Silt percentage	0.0124	Irrigated mother crop	0.0086
Variations in mother crop	0.0113	Precipitation CQ	0.0086
Median wind gust WQ	0.0104	Median wind speed WSQ	0.0084
Sand percentage	0.0103	Variations	0.0084
pH	0.0102	Volunteer plants in mother crop	0.0083
Exchangeable Na	0.0101	Irrigated	0.0083
Annual hours of high RH	0.0101	Planting DOY	0.0082
Total P ₂ O ₅	0.0100	Volunteer plants	0.0058
Isothermality	0.0099	Field area	0.0034
Mean temperature WSQ	0.0098	Pre-basic	0.0014

WQ = warmest quarter, RH = relative humidity, DOY = day of year, WSQ = wettest quarter, DM = driest month, DQ = driest quarter, CQ = coldest quarter. Values represent the importance of each feature's contribution to the model.